

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Appendice A

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 5.2

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – M4C2 1.5 of PNRR funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036).

LITERATURE REVIEW

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1 Introduction

The SMART WEST project would like to provide analyses, best practices, intervention lines, tools, and devices to fully exploit the potential of hybrid and remote working to enhance business performance and improve worker wellbeing and enable companies to organize these models of work effectively and orderly in the mountain areas of the NODES ecosystem, including the southern regions participating in the project, as Basilicata.

The first step is to deeply analyse the literature on this topic. The emerging literature on remote working is by its nature multidisciplinary. Indeed, this theme has impacts on various branches of science such as engineering, economics, computer science, sociology, architecture, and law. Although it required considerable effort, it was decided to organize the literature review on the five themes of the project and not on the different scientific branches. This approach made it possible to consider the theme in its complexity and multidimensionality. It should also allow you to proceed more consistently and linearly in the next steps of industrial research.

Therefore, as the project, even this literature review will be developed around five modules: 1) new smart working tools and devices; 2) digital compliance and cyber security; 3) costs and performance; 4) organizational change; 5) wellbeing and satisfaction of workers. Note that these literature reviews partially overlap with each other and have strong connections to each other, influencing each other as follows:

Figure 1 The theoretical framework

Indeed, adopting remote or hybrid forms of work requires new tools and devices (module 1) and a new economic and legislative framework to provide guarantees and incentives for companies and workers (module 2). A new framework and new tools and devices drive (and are driven by) a revision of the organizational structure of the company (module 4). A new organizational structure and new tools and devices have an impact both on the costs and performance of the company (module 3) and on wellbeing, lifestyle, free time, and career of workers (module 5).

2 New remote working tools and devices

2.1 Opportunities for enterprises and workers

2.1.1 *The legacy of the pandemic*

With the rapid growth of remote work mode due to the coronavirus pandemic, organizations and employees quickly had to adapt to processes and practices related to the constant use of technologies to carry out remote work. The basic technology for a rapid increase in remote work mode was already widely available in most developed countries: fast and reliable Internet access, e-mail, conference tools, etc. [1]. Daily activities, such as meeting and social interactions with colleagues, must be reconsidered and facilitated to work comprehensively and efficiently [2]. There is concern about the decrease or lack of sociability among employees who operate exclusively or partially in remote work mode. This mode influences the ability of employees to maintain social relations with colleagues [3, 4]. The rapid adaptation of workers suggests that remote employees should be able to maintain communication through different technological means, allowing individuals to feel more socially present [5]. Among the risks highlighted for the transition to remote work, there is the isolation of collaboration network, it emerged that there are fewer new connections in different work groups. From the data analysed in literature it is clear that the network has become more static, with fewer connections added each month [6].

The most widely used remote working tools include: cloud systems, Virtual Private Network (VPN), instant messaging tools, cooperation platforms and corporate communication. Some of the technologies listed were already used as a support tool for office work, for example many companies already used data storage services (cloud). Especially in companies where this did not happen, the literature also describes the disadvantages of remote working technologies, in particular considering security and privacy [7]. Privacy is a concern because being always connected can lead to conflicts between work and family life [8]. During the emergency phase of the pandemic, security and confidentiality of the tools were undervalued issues compared to the usefulness of the services provided. In this post-emergency phase, these aspects must be considered in order to reduce the critical issues of these tools and enhance their advantages [9].

In this project we want to provide solutions for an efficient remote working that allows employees to have at home or in co-working spaces, the advantages of office work and those of remote working thanks to the support of innovative devices and tools.

2.1.2 *A new future of work*

The impact of remote work on individual productivity and wellbeing was one of many subjects examined in the Microsoft New Future of Work Report 2022 [10]. Workers have shown a preference for hybrid over other modes, at least for the time being. According to a recent research, United States (US) workers prefer work flexibility above non-trivial percentages of their compensation (9%) [11]. The potential drawbacks of working outside of the workplace are also recognized, though. Less socializing (61%) and lesser leadership presence (42%), according to a Glint (2021) survey of LinkedIn members, are the main complaints voiced by employees who work even partially outside of the office [12].

The environment may have an impact on productivity. In uncontrolled work environments like residences, issues like air quality, lighting, temperature, and others are frequently something to look into. These factors have been linked in research to significant changes in productivity, which raises questions about some work environments, particularly unregulated ones like the home office environment. In addition to playing a monitoring role, technologies can help reduce some dangerous elements.

The way people split their personal and professional lives is another issue that has come to light. Some people separate their job and personal lives to prevent them from interfering with one another [13], but this is challenging when they coexist in the same space (for example, when people work remotely).

Workers have experienced the feeling of being "always on" as a result of the shift to remote working and the removal of geographical boundaries. Technology can help with this as well. Currently, there are tools that enable employees to unplug after work, reduce stress, and enhance employee wellbeing [14].

The way people track their productivity and schedule their time for work and life has also changed as a result of remote work. Making time for leisure might help employees find time for personal projects and lessen the stress of a meeting overload [15]. This is another reason why technology can save users' lives by recommending, when practical, the timing of some events and allocating work hours free of meetings.

2.1.3 A new geography of work

In terms of the geography of work, a new period known as the era of hybrid work is beginning. The transition between eras is frequently fuelled by new technologies. Office, Outlook, and Teams are examples of digital tools that will influence the hybrid work period. People can utilize digital technology to comprehend the changes in the way space is used for work, replace space (for instance, meetings), and integrate space (for example, helping people use offices in new ways).

New eras in the geography of labour typically bring both new obstacles as well as numerous significant advantages (such as increased living standards) (e.g. an uneven distribution of such standards). The tech industry will need to put in a lot of effort to not exclude specific demographics [16].

Interest in post-emergency innovation jobs is spreading geographically. In the period 2005-2017, 90% of the employment growth of the innovation sector in the United States (high-tech "advanced" industries and Research and Development (R&D)) occurred only in 5 big cities: Seattle, Boston, San Francisco, San Diego and San Jose [17]. As a result, there is now a wider salary disparity between the most prosperous urban areas and the rest. Since 2020, interest in tech, science, and engineering occupations in the United States has increased everywhere, particularly in rural counties, reducing the gap between urban and rural areas [18, 19]. Not all the employees who have the possibility to work from home have fast and reliable internet connection. Only 65% of Americans said their internet was fast enough to handle video calling in a 2020 survey. The remaining 35% had not a strong enough internet connection at home to work from there [20]. In the US, 24% of rural adults, compared to 9% of suburban adults and 13% of urban adults, think that having high-speed Internet connection is a serious issue in their neighbourhood [21]. The evolution of society must also consider this aspect in order to allow citizens to work also from rural areas in order to repopulate these areas.

Only a minority of global jobs can be done remotely. In all countries, between 5% and 26% of the workforce can work in remote work more than half of the time without loss of productivity [22]. Globally, 80% of the workforce cannot work from home, the top 8 sectors without this possibility are: agriculture, education, healthcare, retail, hospitality, manufacturing, transport and construction, with 2.7 billion employed workers [23].

2.2 Opportunities for supporting technologies

2.2.1 Key supporting technologies for remote working and its extensions

Remote work is a set of modern and not-conventional organizational models that are characterized by high flexibility in the choice of the working spaces, time and tools, and that provides all employees of an organization with the best working conditions to accomplish their tasks. While it generally considered for activities and jobs that can be executed from a PC, working locally or acting on remote servers/facilities, it is also to be considered and extended to a plethora of current and foreseeable tasks that moves towards Industry 5.0 paradigms, like micro smart additive manufacturing enterprises, predictive maintenance and hyper customization services, cyber physical cognitive systems within an overall better and deeper integration between the creativity of human experts and efficient, intelligent and accurate machines [24, 25]. Key supporting technologies, above trivial preconditions like an efficient, ubiquitous and reliable data connectivity and the support of adequate IT (Information Technology) tools and proper related UX (User experience) metaphors, are advancements in the implementation of as edge computing, digital twins, collaborative robots, Internet of everything, blockchain, and 6G and beyond networks [26, 27].

A shortlist, non-exclusive, of common problems and associated solutions can be built paradigmatically around four initial topics: the environment (at home and at work), information sharing, asynchronous meetings, and hybrid meetings.

Environment

Environments both at home and at work could be having an impact on productivity. Environmental components such as temperature, lighting, and air quality are frequently ignored in workplace settings. It is concerning that some work conditions, both at home and at the office, are connected by research to significant changes in productivity. Several studies can show that, for example, chess tournament players made more mistakes because of increased PM2.5 (Particulate Matter) indoor air pollution [28, 29], or loud settings had a negative impact on motivation and memory while also making people feel more exhausted [30], or that the noise pollution brought on by more remote phone conversations is a significant open research subject [31]. Therefore, within our context, we could see opportunities for devices that can monitor temperature, humidity, sound, and pollution (incl. PM10, PM2.5) and devices that can stop/limit the noise pollution brought on by remote phone conversations or other devices in the surroundings of remote work environments.

Information sharing

For distant teams, impromptu and chance conversation is still challenging. Opportunistic casual conversation is more difficult in remote and hybrid teams, yet it is essential for trust, morale, and information exchange. Informal conversation might be structured temporarily around social routines. As an example, several studies confirmed that during COVID-19, the absence of casual conversation at the water cooler, in the hallway or breakroom, when people entered or exited meetings, etc., was felt deeply [32, 33, 34, 35]. Therefore, social rituals, which offer opportunities for interaction and a feeling of enduring team culture, should be organized by teams [32, 34]. Spatial environments may create more opportunities for casual conversation throughout the day as well as before and after meetings (see also "Spatial environments are favourable to ad hoc engagement") [36]. We see opportunities for tools/features that can support and make easier information sharing and groups interactions, with effective and easy control of alerts, reminders and feedbacks.

Asynchronous meetings

The information choice and overload issues with pre-meeting materials, parallel conversation, and post-meeting catch-up may be improved with the use of advanced information filtering and

summarizing technologies. Since February 2020, the typical Teams user has spent 252% more time per week in meetings [37]. Improving async cooperation holds the possibility of increasing the effectiveness of meetings and decreasing their workload [38]. Large language models and summarizing techniques can transform unstructured conference content into structured async artifacts like notes and action items for catch-up and interaction following meetings [39]. Opportunities can lay here for tools that can automatically summarize meetings and can support asynchronous meetings.

Hybrid meetings

A specific problem, called ‘The Leaf Blower Problem’, arises when a substantial interruption (such as a leaf blower or children) only affects one side of a conversation and is only perceptible to individuals on that side of the conversation, causing significant confusion in the discourse [40]. The grounding error is an ancient issue in human-centered AI (artificial intelligence) and UX design: when there is a gap in our shared understanding, grounding errors occur. A related issue is the absence of reciprocity in perception, or the inability to know how others view us [41]. This issue is particularly problematic in talks conducted through technology, which in turn supports and adds to the challenge of turn-taking in video calls. Early study on video communication [42, 43] demonstrated how the flow of a discussion is broken and interaction turns into an effortful performance when one is always concerned with how one is heard and seen. Hybrid meetings, where the inequalities in perception are magnified, make this situation worse. We can envisage here opportunities for devices and services that allow a better video communication, both in terms of mere quality (i.e. more resolution, better focusing, better light, clearer audio, with noise suppression, etc.) and/or experience (i.e. the need of UI elements that reassure about how others seeing my screen, or listening my voice, or if can follow my slides, etc.).

Other technologies like Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, or other mix of media technologies for hybrid fruitions, can be a great advantage in order to allow an overall more effective and meaningful experiences [44].

Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality tools and devices had a long history of implementations (or, at least, prototypes) for business applications, especially for on-site maintenance tasks, for simulation activities (for rendering and visualizing newly designed objects before actually realizing them), or training activities [45]. A part from other successful applications in specific domains, like healthcare (i.e., rehabilitation and/or exercising) or tourism (i.e., virtual or augmented museums) [46, 47], other attempts into implementing VR/MR (Virtual and Mixed Reality) solutions to foster collaboration and enhance remote working [48, 49] are struggling to find commercial viability into products and services. In fact, while existing services are shutting down or trying hard to maintain rather than increase their users [50, 51, 52, 53], others are focused to relaunch themselves and reshape their offerings for business applications [54, 55]. Some of the key elements that are currently stopping users and workers in adopting them can be categorized into two main groups: those related to technical aspects, and those related to experiential aspects.

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3 Digital compliance and cyber security

3.1 Introduction

Over the last decade, buzzwords such as 'Industry 4.0' and 'Work 4.0' have become increasingly popular and have now entered common usage. The former refers to the whole set of changes that have affected technology, business, and society in the 21st century due to the deployment of tools that favour interconnectivity and automation. The latter concerns a trend that has developed in response to the changes brought about by Industry 4.0, i.e., the set of transformations and innovations that have taken place in the world of work as a result of an increasing process of digitisation of work activities and the evolution of Information and Communications Technologies. Traditional ways of working, based on fixed workplaces and clear timetables, have been joined by new forms based on the idea that, thanks to suitable technological supports, work can be done from anywhere and at any time.

In the light of this, a relevant consequence can be seen in the way work is performed. Reference must be made to telework or remote work, meaning work performed by the employee outside the place of work. This phenomenon began to develop in the United States in the 1970s, but despite the predictions made in the 1980s that it would become the dominant work mode, it did not really take hold for a long time, remaining a practice to which limited recourse was made. The COVID-19 pandemic has had significant repercussions in this respect [1]. Indeed, as is well known, in order to contain the spread of the virus, governments took measures restricting freedom of movement. This led to a slowdown in production activities deemed non-essential and a significant push in favour of the use of remote working or agile working, i.e., work carried out without time or place constraints through the use of technological tools [2][3]. According to the available data, 48% of European workers worked from home at least once during the pandemic period and 34% did so exclusively. Thus, it has gradually been acknowledged that remote working has many advantages for workers, insofar as it can lead to greater autonomy, increased productivity and reduced commuting times. Therefore, remote working as a new model of ubiquitous and non-temporal work is now a reality [4].

However, problems may arise with regard to the effective respect of working hours, work-life balance, and cybersecurity.

Cybersecurity is one of the main challenges faced by companies in the context of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), in which a number of smart devices associated with machines, computers and people are networked and communicate with each other. In this connected industrial scenario, personnel need to be aware of cybersecurity issues in order to prevent or minimize the occurrence of cybersecurity incidents and corporate data breaches, and thus to make companies resilient to cyber-attacks. In addition, the recent increase in remote working due to the COVID-19 pandemic means that the need for cybersecurity awareness is more relevant than ever [2].

3.2 Digital compliance

Digital compliance refers to compliance on the part of an organization with minimum security and privacy requirements [5] [6].

Home working has been one of the long-promised freedoms of information technology. But until recently it was something that relatively few people had routinely experienced in practice (aside, perhaps, from taking work home to do in the evenings and at weekends). This situation abruptly changed in early 2020, with the COVID-19 pandemic forcing organizations to shut their doors and send staff home. Across the globe, home working wherever possible became the standard advice, and technology was the fundamental enabler of the change [3]. Where necessary, change in the relevant legislation has been introduced in order to make it possible for home working to be performed.

This is where the issue of the right to disconnect comes in. Defined by some as the right to privacy of the 21st century [5], it is seen as a remedy that allows the worker to remain selectively online, hence, to be unavailable, without any negative consequences in terms of salary or continuation of the employment [6][7][8]. Therefore, through it, the aim is to deal with the phenomenon of staff hyper-connection to company tools even beyond working hours, given the detrimental effects that this could have on employees' physical and mental health and allowing them to enjoy their free time. Thus, it can be regarded as the worker's right to unavailability that protects the worker from non-stop work. There is no shortage of those who believe it should be regarded as a new way to express the worker's right to rest [9], while others qualify it, rather than as a right of the worker, as a duty incumbent on the employer [10].

Furthermore, issues may be raised regarding prevention and protection measures related to the performance of work activities outside the company premises, such as risk assessment, the provision to workers of timely information on general and activity-specific risks, training on how to perform agile activities, the appropriateness of the working environment, and work-related ergonomics. Italy has adopted a regulation in this field, which provides for criminal sanctions should the relevant obligations not be met. This may be a testbed as to the protection of workers, which deserves attention since, as of today, no significant doctrinal analysis has been provided.

3.3 Cyber security

The adoption of remote work calls for appropriate means for protecting the user and the company from malicious cyber-attacks and from exposure of data to unwanted eyes. At national and international level, many initiatives are promoted in order to increase awareness of the most common threats and reduce naive behaviour and, thus, reduce possible damages.

Following [11], traditional cybersecurity strategies are often vulnerable to insider threats due to a long-established practice focused on perimeter security. Employees already have access to valuable organizational data. A hacker can infiltrate a single vulnerable user account and encrypt thousands of files without being noticed. Experts generally agree that well-intentioned but careless employees pose as much danger to an organization's cybersecurity as hackers on the outside: 90% of successful hack attacks or incidents are ascribed to human error or behaviour. In most cases, employees of certain companies receive some information security training when they join a company, but typically this training is not repeated on a routine basis. Teleworkers are also subject to "social engineering" via working remotely in public spaces where hacking, shoulder-surfing, and dumpster-diving are prevalent. Social engineering is an attack vector that relies heavily on human interaction that involves manipulating people into breaking normal security protocols and best practices in order to gain access to computer systems, networks or physical locations for financial or other gain. These techniques lure unsuspecting users into providing business confidential and personally identifiable information. Once the data are obtained, the attacker then tries to infect computer systems and networks with malware, e.g. by sending e-mails with attachments containing computer viruses and network worms, phishing and pharming hooks, and encouraging the overall use of public networks, mobile device apps, and infected external drives.

According to [22], solid cybersecurity awareness and effective implementations of cybersecurity practices are essential for companies to: (i) prevent cyber threats, especially those affecting employees; (ii) reduce the associated business risks; and (iii) ensure the security and stability of systems, while improving the effectiveness of processes across the organisation. In order for the level of cybersecurity awareness to be such that employees act correctly, the literature suggests that they must:

- Be aware of threats and be able to identify possible occurrences;
- Be able to assess both the immediate and long-term impact of cyber-attacks;
- Be conscious of how an attack can evolve over time;
- Be able to understand the attacker's intentions;
- Be aware of the conditions that facilitate attacks;
- Have evaluated the information that is needed to make decisions during an attack;
- Be updated about the possible actions attackers might take to achieve their intent. For this reason, cybersecurity awareness and training initiatives are important and should be repeated over time [2].

A number of international organizations' efforts are devoted to promote awareness and spread updated knowledge about cybersecurity threats. The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) is one of the most active organizations, putting education of the online user as one of its main goals especially after the coronavirus pandemics. Every year ENISA, together with the European Commission and the Member States, organizes a campaign that is dedicated to 1) promoting cybersecurity among EU citizens and organizations, and 2) providing up-to-date online security information through awareness raising activities and sharing of good practices. The general intention is to help EU citizens develop a basic understanding of the different types of online security and privacy issues. The slogan 'Cybersecurity is a Shared Responsibility' well represents the approach. In the last ten years, this joint effort has seen the month of October as dedicated to special themes, 2022 being dedicated to phishing and ransomware. The campaign not only promotes a safer use of the Internet, but also provides the knowledge and tools to do so.

ENISA also published some simple tips [14] for workers and organizations, including:

- Use of corporate (rather than personal) computers without mixing work and leisure activities on the same device.
- Connect to the internet via secure networks; avoid open/free networks to avoid people in the vicinity to hijack the connection)
- Avoid the exchange of sensitive company information through possibly insecure connections and possibly use corporate Intranet resources to share working files.
- Data on local drives should be encrypted.
- Antivirus / Antimalware must be installed and be fully updated.
- Do not share the virtual meeting URLs on social media or other public channels.

Interestingly, since remote work does not mean work from home but may mean work from public places, like libraries, coffee-shops or co-working spaces, they also suggest to lock the screen when not at the computer.

EUROPOL EC3 (European Cybercrime Center) has developed intuitive infographics [15], in all the official languages of the European Union, to explain the basic strategies for making each home safer a reduce exposure to cyber crimes.

In the UK, the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) usefully provided a summary of key issues that organisations should be addressing, supported by related poster and e-learning materials for staff. The NCSC had also already devised a set of 'top tips' for staying secure online, among other new guidance packages around home working, video conferencing and moving business online, which were emphasised and promoted during the COVID-19 lockdown period. While these are by no means a full answer to the issue of secure end-user behaviour, they are certainly a good set of core practices to follow:

- Protect your email by using a strong and separate password.
- Install the latest software and app updates.
- Turn on two-factor authentication on your email.
- Password managers – how they help you secure passwords.
- Secure smartphones and tablets with a screen lock.
- Always backup your most important data [3].

3.4 Final Remarks

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, the level playing field has changed. The legislative framework has had to adapt to a context different from the previously existing one in order to make it easier for businesses and organisations to make use of the potential of remote working. The resort to this modality of work has made it possible to balance economic demands with health protection requirements, but it also carries risks related for instance to the protection of the workers' rights, such as in the case of the right to disconnect, and security issues. Therefore, the legislative framework must be updated so to take into account new issues.

However, awareness of the risks of remote working is not just a consequence of the isolation due to the pandemics. Already in 2016 the American National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) provided guidelines on telework and remote access to help organizations mitigate security risks associated with the enterprise technologies used for teleworking, such as remote access servers, telework client devices, and remote access communications. The guideline was updated a couple of years ago [12].

Many resources are already available to the small or medium enterprises to face the cyber risks of remote work. First, the standard ISO/IEC 27001:2013 [16] specifies the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an information security management system within the context of the organization. The requirements set out in ISO/IEC 27001:2013 are generic and are intended to be applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size or nature. Very recently a guideline [13] was published to raise awareness of such standard in Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and help its adoption. The guideline well explains both the need of data privacy and the tools for enacting it and the protection of the ICTs of the company.

SME companies have lagged in their adoption of technology and the security protections necessary to manage their risk effectively [23]. They cannot afford to look away as cybersecurity preparedness is key to sustenance and survival in today's digital environment [24]. The Consumer Data Protection Act proposed by Senator Ron Wyden of Oregon is seeking to impose significant sanctions on executives and companies not being proactive and diligent. The penalties could be as severe as "jail time of up to 20 years for executives who knowingly sign off on incorrect or inaccurate annual certifications of their companies' data-security practices" [25]. The bill also recommends a fine of up to 4% of a company's annual revenue.

When executives need to evaluate their current level of cybersecurity readiness, they could adopt the cybersecurity evaluation tool (CET) tool. This methodology will not only help identify strengths and weaknesses, but it also makes best-practice recommendations for how to plug security loopholes effectively. In other words, by using an evaluation methodology, IT leaders can quickly:

- Identify their greatest vulnerabilities;
- Compare their maturity to their peers based on a set of standard measures; and
- Choose the most valuable improvement efforts.

SMEs cannot afford to delay. Every company surveyed fell well below the ideal level of maturity recommended by the SME CET. Every reasonable effort made to take stock of the state of information security and act on the recommendations is a step in the right direction. At least the striving company will be in a credible position to respond to this fundamental post-breach question: Did the institution make every reasonable effort to proactively secure sensitive data? [4].

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4. Costs and performance

The general debate on remote working (also called home working or teleworking) has become passionate and heated among enterprises, which have been practicing it for some years following the interest it has raised as a feasible response that is able to balance often contrasting needs (efficiency and productivity on the company's side, and flexibility and work life balance on the individual's side) and so to create enhanced working conditions [1].

Despite in literature there is a lack of studies about remote working and the impact on performance, a study conducted by Ko et al. [2] reported empirical evidence that proves the use and effectiveness of remote work. Unlike previous studies that had primarily focused on one-dimensional aspects of remote work respectively, this study took an integrated approach to propose a comprehensive framework. This research examined aspects of work attitude (job satisfaction) and work performance (task performance) together. As employees' attitudes and work performance have a major impact on organizational performance, these two have been the most frequently studied subjects in the individual-organization research.

More specifically this study contributes to verifying the relationship between work attitude and work performance. On top of the above theoretical implications, the following insights for practice are drawn from this research.

First, this study implies that focusing only on employing technologies is insufficient to promote remote work company-wide. Organizations/companies are able to reap the benefits of remote work only when remote work appropriation takes place, which indicating that it is necessary to consider structural and motivational dimensions together that affect remote work appropriation. In other words, it is important to clearly understand different reasons why users choose remote work and create a structure in which remote work is smoothly accepted. Therefore, understanding every dimension comprehensively, rather than leaning towards a single perspective, would help achieve synergy among benefits resulting from remote work appropriation [3].

Second, the findings illustrate that it is necessary to consider the characteristics of tasks and organizational environment as well as system quality when building remote work systems. Even with a high-quality remote work platform, remote work appropriation will not work properly if it does not suit job characteristics and organizational environment. Therefore, individual roles and tasks need to be inter-connected, and more autonomy should be given through empowerment.

Third, it is essential to exactly understand employees' motivation regarding why they are using remote work. Although the organization is structured to promote remote work systems, the use of remote work is determined by employees' choice. If companies or organizations pay attention to employees' motivation or reasons to use remote work and how they can support their employees, they can make remote work more suitable for employees and the whole organization.

Lastly, perceived ease of use was found to have the greatest impact on remote work appropriation among six antecedents reported in this study. This finding illustrates that ease of using devices or services supporting remote work leads to substantial levels of appropriation. Therefore, companies need to put more priority on building user-friendly platforms and supporting services [2].

Another research designed a randomized experiment on a sample of workers in a large Italian company: workers are randomly divided into a treated group that engages in flexible space and time job (which we call "smart-working") one day per week for 9 months and a control group that continues to work traditionally. By comparing the treated and control workers, causal evidence was identified that the flexibility of smart working increases the productivity of workers and improves their well-being and work-life balance. We also observe that the effects are stronger for women and that there are no significant spillover effects within workers of a team [4].

Research found that remote work can enhance workplace, work time, and infrastructural flexibility, leading to improved employee satisfaction and productivity and organizational performance. The study proposes a model that can be applied to other emerging economies to investigate the impact of remote work on organizational flexibility. This model may serve as a baseline for future research on remote work in different geographic locations [5]. Indeed, the scope is not only to draw up a picture of smart working, but the goal is also to capture the maturity of the remote work, considering data from different geographies to derive any geographical and country-specific factors that influence drivers of remote analytics empowerment capability and their holistic effects on customer linking and firm performance [5].

At the same time another study confirms that empowerment is an enabler of dynamic capabilities, and an analytically empowered workforce contributes to firm performance. The article concludes with managerial implications for senior managers responsible for overseeing employees and ensuring their well-being in a remote work environment. They must focus on making analytics technology accessible to all employees, ensure that tools are intuitive, and eliminate duplication to facilitate remote employees in leveraging analytics and enhancing organizational performance [6].

The literature background is not well aligned, indeed another research shows that the output generated from working from home is generally lower by a negligible level of 0.5-0.8%, this shows that there is no real difference between working from home and working in office in terms of output, the only real difference is that monitoring the output of workers is easier in the office rather than from home [7].

Finally, it is evident the literature gap about remote working and company performance that must be fulfilled.

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5. Organizational change

Remote working is a set of modern and not-conventional organizational models that are characterized by high flexibility in the choice of the working spaces, time and tools, and that provides all employees of an organization with the best working conditions to accomplish their tasks. We report about the state of art on remote working from three different perspectives, each of which encompasses a number of challenges: 1) organizational, that is, how should the organization be redefined in order to accommodate remote working in an effective way; 2) sociological, that is, which is the impact of remote working on the local communities and on society; and 3) technological, that is, the trend in computer science on the representation and management of processes of activities involving many actors.

5.1 Challenges on the design of organizations

The general debate on remote working has become passionate and heated among enterprises, which have been practicing it for some years following the interest it has raised as a feasible response that is able to balance often contrasting needs (efficiency and productivity on the company's side, and flexibility and work life balance on the individual's side) and so to create enhanced working conditions [1]. The same happens in the field of consultancy, where the goal is to offer support in organizing fitting solutions and in defining how to manage them, being evident that the requested change by the new model has relevant implications for organizational culture, for HR practices design, for the relationships between bosses and workers, and for the definitions of specific objectives necessary to guide and evaluate work.

Remote Working enables people to benefit from greater work flexibility, advancing individual control over organizational activities, but it may impair interpersonal exchanges at work, disrupting job meaningfulness. The research conducted in [2] encompasses a sample of 30,932 employees and findings suggest that remote working triggers a positive sense of the significance of work. However, it negatively affects interpersonal relationships (IR) with peers and supervisors, entailing professional and spatial isolation. Impaired IR twists the positive implications of remote working on organizational meaningfulness (OM), curtailing the employees' sense of significance at work. The research findings suggest that while remote working triggers a positive sense of the significance of work, it negatively affects IR with peers and supervisors, entailing professional and spatial isolation. Remote working is a double-edged sword. It contributes to the enrichment of OM, enhancing the individual self-determination to shape the spatial context of work. However, its side effects on interpersonal exchanges generate a drift toward organizational meaninglessness. Tailored management interventions intended to sustain IR at work are needed to fit the design of remote working arrangements to the employees' evolving social needs. Another research, conducted on Twitter [3], showed that users associate Remote Working mainly to positive emotions and to a better work-life balance.

The recent unexpected and quick acceleration in the development and diffusion of new technologies supporting communication, collaboration, and social networking, together with the pervasive dissemination of powerful and easy-to-use mobile devices, helps the growth of portable systems and offers new opportunities for innovative solutions regarding when to work, where to work, and in which way to work further having impacts on the so-called remote work environment, which is a flourishing field of studies parallel to the one of remote working on which the research in [1] focuses. This is exactly how the collective imagination and a certain sort of rhetoric are used to represent the

sort of working in relaxing conditions with better performance that is associated with the remote working model, which has become the premise for its adoption.

The literature review conducted by [1] shows as in three papers remote working is associated with workplace and work behaviour [4]. With regard to the workplace, changes in layout and space redesign are connected with the role of more and more essential technologies. Related to work behaviours, it is underlined how HR practices have to be redesigned in order to support new ways of working. A really important element is ICTs, which are present in six papers. ICTs or the adoption of ICTs are indicated among the keywords often associated with the technology acceptance model and with perceived usefulness. In more detail, a first group is engaged in studying how the three basic elements (ICT, human resources, and layout) work to build the new model.

One key issue is the importance of leadership to pursue behavioural, cultural, technological, and ethical aspirations of remote working practices in order to develop a comprehensive understanding of leadership in remote working contexts. Research suggested that smart leadership is about finding a balance between soft power (i.e., achieving outcomes by attracting and persuading), and hard power (i.e., using rewards or punishments). The notion of leadership in remote working contexts does not represent a new idea; what emerges as important is that such leadership should be seen as a naturally emerging behaviour that combines agile logics and change management practices to align interests at different levels of the organization [5].

This study provides important implications for research. First, it examined what needs to be considered to promote the use of remote work from structuration aspects, and what motivation factors influence remote work from individual aspects. The results reveal that most factors drawn from AST and TAM facilitate remote working appropriation, which, in turn, brings better performance and increased job satisfaction. This study reported empirical evidence that proves the use and effectiveness of remote working. Second, as for the effects of remote work, this study examined aspects of work attitude (job satisfaction) and work performance (task performance) together. As employees' attitudes and work performance have a major impact on organizational performance, these two have been the most frequently studied subjects in the individual-organization research. While there is no denying that job satisfaction and task performance are the major variables representing organizational effectiveness, there are divided views on the causality between the two. Each dimension of remote working appropriation leads to a different outcome (i.e., task performance, job satisfaction), but the outcome variables are inter-connected (i.e., job satisfaction was found to influence task performance). Focusing on companies that wish to establish a remote working system, this study examined the causality between employees' job satisfaction and task performance and finally provided empirical evidence of it. By doing so, this study contributes to verifying the relationship between work attitude and work performance.

On top of the above theoretical implications, the following insights for practice are drawn from this research. First, this study implies that focusing only on employing technologies is insufficient to promote remote working company-wide. Organizations/companies are able to reap the benefits of remote working only when remote working appropriation takes place, which indicates that it is necessary to consider structural and motivational dimensions together that affect remote working appropriation. In other words, it is important to clearly understand different reasons why users choose remote working and create a structure in which remote working is smoothly accepted. Therefore, understanding every dimension comprehensively, rather than leaning towards a single perspective, would help achieve synergy among benefits resulting from remote working

appropriation. Second, the findings illustrate that it is necessary to consider the characteristics of tasks and organizational environment as well as system quality when building remote working systems. Even with a high-quality remote working platform, remote working appropriation will not work properly if it does not suit job characteristics and organizational environment. Therefore, individual roles and tasks need to be inter-connected, and more autonomy should be given through empowerment. Third, it is essential to exactly understand the employees' motivation regarding why they are using remote working. Although the organization is structured to promote remote working systems, the use of remote working is determined by employees' choice. If companies or organizations pay attention to employees' motivation or reasons to use remote working and how they can support their employees, they can make remote working more suitable for employees and the whole organization. Lastly, perceived ease of use was found to have the greatest impact on remote working appropriation among six antecedents reported in this study. This finding illustrates that ease of using devices or services supporting remote work leads to substantial levels of appropriation. Therefore, companies need to put more priority on building user-friendly platforms and supporting services [6].

Empirical evidence suggests that the managers who aim to fully benefit from remote working practices should not only invest in the enabling digital technologies, but also make the complementary transformations in organizational policies and workspace settings, according to the contingent conditions under which they operate [4]. Technological advances have made possible industrial and commercial applications of artificial intelligence, virtual reality and highly integrated manufacturing systems. It has also freed business activity from a focus on place, as both work activities and markets have been able to harness information and communication technologies in order to operate remotely. As a result, researchers have highlighted a phenomenon of 'smart' working. Some have pointed to a fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0) in which 'smart' factories use robotics to achieve high performance. There is now a suggestion of progress towards Industry 5.0, in which technological and social systems work in harmony to deliver personalized mass customization of products and services. Considering the perspective of unique, individual understandings of work roles and sustainability, some questions need to find an answer. Among these, since remote work is often associated to so called smart systems, the questions 'Smart' from whose point of view? Do "smart" systems promote sustainable organizations? How should the design of "smart" systems be approached? The general feeling is that contemporary socio-technical systems approach to organizational analysis are the best way to support harnessing of smart technologies in organizations [7].

Interpersonal relationships are key in both distant and face-to-face exchanges. They also help to understand which management practices can influence perceived proximity. In particular, they help to understand the role of communication and collective culture and support the importance of the e-leader [8]. Managers should adopt digital technologies judiciously in the age of pervasive technology rather than installing readily accessible, off-the-shelf alternatives [9]. Additional ramifications for managers are related to particular user needs and unforeseen effects of the technologies used. Without assuming that people are already tech-savvy, managers would benefit from viewing the learning curve in businesses as a severe tech-support issue. Additionally, there are repercussions for lawmakers regarding technology use and labor regulations to safeguard workers' privacy, safety, and well-being. Laws governing the design and (re)use of areas can aid in reducing the dangers linked to migrations to more remote working.

5.2 Remote Working challenges from sociological and psychological literature

From the individual point of view of male and female workers, we can count among the advantages of remote working [10, 11, 12] the saving of time and costs related to commuting, which also translates into greater freedom in choosing where to reside; greater autonomy and accountability in carrying out one's duties thanks to a different way of working and interacting; on the other hand, there is the risk of developing a sense of isolation both professionally and socially, as well as having to take into account any negative repercussions for career prospects. Furthermore, the same element can be a pro or a con; the example of the reconciliation of times and places between working life and private life is paradigmatic, which can bring great benefits or bitter conflicts depending on how it is managed.

From the point of view of companies, the studies show an increase in productivity and corporate flexibility (if duly accompanied by an organizational modernization whose costs and risks are to be evaluated); a decrease in costs related to the rent and utilities of the offices for access to the premises of a smaller number of collaborators [13]; an increase in those related to ICTs that must be able to support remote work; furthermore, if, on the one hand, the different remote personnel management seems to guarantee less absenteeism [14], on the other, it poses new challenges due to the need to adapt and update the methods through which it is exercised.

Among the effects on a social level, the literature highlights the reduction of traffic and therefore of pollution, as well as the consequences on the real estate market, on transport, on trade [11, 12, 15].

While not directly related, some of these factors may also have implications for corporate performance. In fact, if the adoption of remote working can increase the motivation of workers or affect their sense of professional and social isolation, this could affect their productivity and therefore the company's results. Likewise, the consequences in the real estate market could have important repercussions on corporate assets and investments.

On the other hand, it is necessary to deal with some reality data. The first is that working anywhere and at any time is an option only for a part of those participating in the labour market. ISTAT [16] identifies types of professions that may be more suitable for this type of work; on the one hand, these are those in which there is supervision and which do not require particular organizational autonomy and, on the other, those in which, on the contrary, there is a lot of autonomy and freedom in defining one's own objectives and in how pursue them and, to a lesser extent and linked to non-deferrable emergencies, teaching and a part of the public employment. Furthermore, the institute records that there are economic sectors in which this is easier (IT, public administration, financial and insurance activities, business services) and that recourse to this method of providing work performance grows as the size increases corporate [52]. The possibility of working from home in 2020 decreased the risk of contagion and in many cases allowed economic activity to continue while preserving the employment of a part of the workforce, even if this further segmented the labour market [17]. Basso and colleagues [18] underline that in Italy about 50% of workers would not be in a position to be able to carry out their work in conditions of safety, given the continuation of the risks associated with the pandemic situation.

The second is the non-uniformity and adequacy of the communication infrastructures which risks severely penalizing some parts of the territory.

It is clear how the topic of remote working is particularly relevant and full of suggestions, especially from a future perspective. In fact, on the one hand, it is part of a process of progressive deconstruction of the methods of regulating the employment relationship, making the three elements that distinguish

the organizational context less rigid: technology, time, the area of work. On the other hand, it cannot ignore the processes of innovation and digitization which are the viaticum of companies that want to increase its competitiveness and survive on the global market.

Spatial flexibility has received less attention in the literature than other aspects related to the introduction of remote forms of work. Recently some studies have tried to deepen this aspect, going to investigate the specific implications related to the places where the work activity is carried out; among these, research conducted by [19] has highlighted how this affects the stress perceived by workers (for example, mobile workers are more affected by the intensification of work than those who work from home).

In fact, as [20] argues, in reality the fact of working "anytime, anywhere" (as people are often prompted to do using ICTs) does not imply that one works everywhere but rather that one does it in specific places that are not what we consider usual.

The critical factors that emerge are linked to the consequences of no longer sharing the same spaces with continuity.

As [21] point out, each work organization is also an important socialization agency that contributes to forming that peculiar social construct which is the individual, professional and collective identity of workers. The co-presence, through a system of rules, processes and incentives, cultivates and cements a sense of corporate identity; in many organizational models, the sense of belonging is an element to be cultivated in order to increase the engagement (and, consequently, the productivity) of the workers. This opens interesting questions about the ability of remote working to provide a sense of corporate identity or whether measures should not be implemented to counteract the sense of isolation that the remote worker may experience [22]. The implications of this way of working are multifaceted and recall, from the point of view of coordination and control, the need to review work processes [23, 24], also opening up the possibility of creating forms of technologically mediated surveillance potentially very pervasive [24].

The critical element is represented by the fact that workers do not have control over how many work communications arrive via device, let alone when this happens [25]. During the time dedicated to private life, male and female workers need to devote themselves to recovery activities (i.e. relaxation, recovery, regeneration) which allow them to set aside the fatigue and stress of working life and then return to it reinvigorated; however, the continuous interruptions to which they may be subjected in the moment of rest can hinder or even prevent this activity and lead to harmful consequences for the serenity (and productivity) of employees, even to burnout [25].

This phenomenon, also known as "time porosity" can lead to a colonization by work time to the detriment of private lifetime. From the point of view of the workers this translates into a lengthening of working times (overwork) or in the perception of working more and in the expectation of responding quickly to any solicitation, with the concrete risk of no longer being able to "unplug" and lead to the risk of work-alcoholism; this term refers to the uncontrolled and compulsive need to work which leads to dedicating a lot of effort and energy to work, diverting them from relationships and activities related to private life, free time and health.

However, the opposite phenomenon can also occur, i.e. the colonization of working time by the private sector. This last phenomenon in the pandemic seems to have been quite common, given that people often found themselves sharing the same spaces with cohabitants who could request their attention while they were working [26]. A trivial example is that of those who had to support their children tackling with distance learning during working hours [27].

Therefore, time flexibility can be a useful resource to increase reconciliation but only if people are able to manage the boundaries between different times, for example by deciding when to look at emails and notifications and when instead to put aside electronic devices.

5.3 Lessons learned on remote working in the pandemic

As [28] underline, digitization does not simply translate into the transition from analogical to digital of documentation (computerization) but also implies an investment in technological equipment and personnel training that allow such information to be treated and processed on video instead of on paper supports. The first element to consider is the availability of suitable devices (laptops, tablets, printers, ...) in terms of number and type of performance required, which is now a prerequisite for making remote work possible.

Research on remote working in the pandemic in which personnel directors of 22 companies in Piedmont were interviewed [19] highlights that the characterizing factors that guided the transition to remote working were the degree of technological development, the organizational structure and corporate culture. In particular, the analysis of the collected material made it possible to look in a more detailed way at the implementation of working from home, inserting it in an articulated framework, made up of the degree of technological-digital innovation, the organizational architecture and the corporate culture of each single company. In light of the specific economic situation and company objectives, the combination of these elements offers a richer interpretation of the strategies adopted and the choices made in the pandemic period. In summary:

- The smallest firms were by far the least ready both for reasons of costs linked to technological and organizational innovation and for the specific type of work performed.
- Most companies seem to have taken the path of technological innovation with substantial ease.
- Innovation linked to work organization seems to be closely interconnected with corporate culture, when this manifests a proactive attitude, oriented towards change management.
- Even among the most avant-garde companies, the suddenness and massive and continuous diffusion of emergency remote working have revealed how many work processes still rely on informal and untraced elements that have suddenly disappeared.

Referring to the same interpretative framework, it is possible to look at the orientations expressed by companies for the future. Most private companies are in favour of introducing some form of remote work. However, it emerges that a hybrid method is desirable, in which there is an alternation between face-to-face work and remote work, which guarantees a balance between employee productivity and well-being and an easy organization of work which increases people's safety and the confidentiality of data. This will require a lot of programming work to organize the coordination of work.

From many quarters - and without any certainty - the ideal mix is identified in 1-2 days of remote working a week. According to many companies, the use of remote working would be very welcome by employees (in one case it is even identified as a company welfare measure) while it would more easily be viewed with greater hostility by management functions, often less oriented towards organizational change.

Among the advantages listed, there is also environmental sustainability. Instead, net of the savings induced by the possibility of reducing corporate spaces, the consequences it could have on productivity in the medium to long term need to be carefully evaluated, especially in relation to innovation, quality and continuous improvement of processes.

Some manufacturing companies among those questioned do not identify in this form of work a benefit for their core business, which sees the pre-eminence of production over services; sometimes this also

seems to derive from the awareness of an unpreparedness on the part of people in terms of (re)organization of work.

For SMEs, undertaking this process of reorganization of work may not be feasible due to excessively high costs.

5.4 Tools for representing, executing, monitoring business processes

Put simply, a business process is a sequence of events or tasks that must be performed for a business to operate [29]. Many companies have repetitive activities that follow some pattern. Lack of organization in such activities can bring along little predictiveness and reduce control over what is going on. This is particularly true when part of the activities is carried out “out of sight”, as it happens when people work remotely. Another issue is to keep track of the ownership of objects/results, that is, who actually concurred to this or that outcome.

Business Process Management systematizes processes, and the way they are communicated and shared, making visible where they start and end, the needed data, the resources, inefficiencies, and so forth. This can be done thanks to approaches, methodologies, and tools for representing, executing (in a computer-supported, partially automatized way), and for verifying business processes. Greater control, greater coordination, and awareness of the weak points to improve are the general benefits. There is also a cost, amounting in part to the effort of learning the new methodologies of operation and tools, and in part to the acquisition of the necessary technological infrastructure. This is the reason why usually such solutions are not adopted by small or medium enterprises. There are, however, many kinds of business process management systems focusing on different facets of business processes. For instance, integration-centric solutions concern processes that involve systems rather than humans. Designing a process is a way to combine existing systems to make them perform a new kind of function, keeping the effort at a high level of abstraction. Other approaches put humans in the centre, allowing to combine tasks performed by workers. A third kind has documents at the centre, and allow making documents follow the right path along a chain of controls, approvals, signatures.

Key players (like Oracle, Red Hat, or Alfresco) that commercialize platforms for business process management typically also supply training programs providing certifications.

Business model management involves many steps, starting with design. The design phase involves interviews with key persons in the company that are knowledgeable about procedures, technical and legal constraints. Processes are then modelled, that is they are represented by means of a typically graphical language. In this phase it is possible to perform “what-if” analysis to investigate alternatives and their consequences, as well as tests with selected future users. Processes are then ready to be executed, that is, to be put at work. Process execution can be monitored to check progress and identify weaknesses, e.g., bottlenecks. Weaknesses can be overcome by changing the process, a phase known as optimization.

Lately a growing interest is being devoted to “process mining”, that is the elicitation of business processes from traces of executions. There are many reasons. Process mining can be a means for building business processes from scratch in contexts where people are more inclined to show what they do rather than to explain what they do. It is also a powerful means for checking compliance of how activities are carried out with respect to how they are expected to be carried out.

In computer science, Business Process Management is a research area that addresses several aspects related to processes, including modelling, discovery, verification, and optimization. Process modelling has been widely investigated in the literature and several general-purpose approaches have been introduced, including, on one side, declarative procedural approaches like Business Process

Modelling Notation (BPMN), Petri Nets, activity diagrams and, on the other side, declarative approaches, like data centric ones [30].

In procedural approaches, a model represents all and only the executions that are allowed. What is not specified is forbidden. Declarative approaches, instead, do not represent executions explicitly but, rather, they represent what is required or forbidden for an execution to be compliant with a model. In essence, all executions that satisfy the requirements are allowed.

Concerning the procedural approaches, BPMN is probably the best known and several tools for modelling processes in BPMN, for executing them, or for verifying them have been proposed. So, for instance, modelling and execution can be done with tools like Bizagi [31], Bonita Software [32], Camunda [33], and Signavio [34].

Once a process is formalized, it is also possible to verify formal properties that may concern it [35 era 6]. To this aim, it is common to use model checking, see for instance [36 era 7]. Model checkers typically require to represent the target properties as temporal logic formulas, either LTL (linear temporal logic) or CTL (computation tree logic) formulas. For instance, [37 era 8] checks the compliance of a process model against a number of patterns, expressed in a graphical language for querying BPMN process models called BPMN-Q. To this aim, the patterns are turned into temporal formulas.

All the mentioned approaches aim at modelling and checking properties that mainly concern the control flow. The reason is that BPMN focuses on the possible executions, while and does not allow an expressive representation of the data concerned in such activities. So, for instance, capturing a location at which some activity should occur is not trivial and calls for the introduction of dependencies that make the model more difficult to understand and more complex [38 era 9]. Declarative approaches adopt a different perspective which, generally, better suit dynamic and collaborative settings, where flexibility is a desired characteristic [39 era 10]. Among the best-known approaches one can find Declare [40 era 11], the case handling paradigm [41 era 12] and Dynamic Condition Response (DCR) Graphs [42 era 13]. Declare is a graphical language with an LTLf formal semantics. An interesting development is Multi-Perspective Declare (MP-Declare), an extension of Declare devised so as to tackle also data and time, besides the control flow. In this framework templates are enriched with an activation condition, which is related to some activating activity and specifies which condition should hold in order for the constraint to be activated; and a target condition, i.e., a condition to be met for the constraint to be fulfilled and concerning some target activity of the constraint. It is also possible to specify a correlation condition that relates aspects of both activities and is evaluated when the target is achieved. Such models can be used for addressing conformance checking, that is verifying that a process instance complies with an MP-Declare process model.

DCR Graphs [42 era 13] resemble at a glance the graphical specification of Declare. Here, however, a graph consists of events and relations among them where relations can be of four kinds: dynamic inclusion, dynamic exclusion, condition and response.

Another declarative approach is the case handling paradigm [43 era 14] which shifts the focus from a flow to a case perspective. A case is seen as a product to be realized; the idea is that the workers need to have at any time all information about a case. So, a case has a structure and a current state, which in turn is represented as a collection of data objects. In 2014 the OMG introduced the Case Management Model and Notation [44 era 15] (CMMN) standard, a graphical notation for case-based process modelling.

The above approaches are known to be activity-centric because they mainly focus on the activities to be performed and their (temporal, ordering) relation. A different perspective is represented by the data-centric approaches, such as the artifact-centric approach [45 era 16] where processes are modelled by considering a number of entities (artifacts) that are relevant in the considered setting. This kind of representation suits those situations where there are a number of well-defined entities to be modelled, and the aim resides in capturing their evolution and interaction. In the artifact centric approach, activities and the order of their execution are hidden inside the artifact specification and its data model and stages. The drawback in this case is that coordination between those agents which perform the activities is not captured explicitly in a way that can be inspected and reasoned about.

Notably, specific application contexts developed, along time, specific solutions for representing processes. Such solutions often do not strictly require computer science support. For instance, the constructions sector traditionally relies on activity-based approaches, like the Critical Path Method (CPM) [46 era 17], and the Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT) [18]. Both basically rely on the definition of activity networks, whose nodes specify the activities and their duration, while arcs represent orderings. Given one such network, it is possible to identify a critical path, that is, a path allowed by the orderings of activities such that if one of the activities on the path is delayed, the overall duration of the project increases. Non-critical paths can be associated with time buffers, capturing that a certain activity delay can be absorbed without increasing the overall duration of the project.

5.5 Final Remarks

Remote Working, as we have seen, creates many challenges on organizations. On the one hand, the individual working remotely faces many difficulties, both practical and personal. On the practical side, the worker is loaded with the burden of creating and maintaining the computer and the tools that enable the remote practice, having to guarantee a degree of security previously unknown; he or she need to understand or build new ways for interacting with colleagues they will not meet in the corridor; he or she will have to manage the working activities together with family activities without the support of a clear schedule. On the personal side, the worker may have a reduced perception of the value of his or her work within the organization, will be estranged from that informal interaction which is so important in every day's work, and, especially if new at work, will have a hard time in acquiring that unique company culture which gives an identity to the company itself. On the managerial side, it is often difficult for the managers to have a clear perception of the work that is actually carried out and to have measures of the performance. On the ICT tools side, even though there are many applications and frameworks that could support winning the mentioned challenges, their cost is high, especially due to the training time needed to master them. Moreover, many of such tools were developed to support work in presence in big firms, thus, they do not provide features that are specifically devised so as to tackle the peculiar drawbacks of remote work.

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6. Wellbeing and satisfaction of workers

Remote working is a way of performing work performance characterized by the intensive use of digital technologies that allow it to be exercised by introducing elements of space-time flexibility [1, 2]. In Italy, before 2020 the use of this tool was marginal [3]. Following the measures to contain the infections linked to the spread of the coronavirus, its use was advocated and used massively [4, 5, 6, 7]. This has allowed many workers and companies to experience it for the first time, albeit with elements of discontinuity with respect to agile work carried out in a non-emergency period, in a "pathological" form [8, 9].

In the following paragraphs, the main findings of recent researches on the relational and social aspects of home working and on the physical comfort and health of people working from homes.

6.1 Regulation, relational aspects and time constraints

The organizational reconfiguration necessary to make its implementation possible and to maximize its potential has repercussions on the regulation of the employment relationship, putting various aspects under tension [1, 2], including the consequences on the well-being of workers [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16]. In particular, the research carried out during the pandemic period in Italy underlined how workers found themselves having a greater availability of time saved by the absence of travel times, time which they used as time for themselves or time for the family depending on their family status. According to the workers, this has increased their well-being [11] and in many cases, even during their returns, has favored the reconciliation between work and life times [18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

However, the risks of overlapping work activities and care tasks must be avoided: the porosity of times must be avoided [6, 13].

Furthermore, in many situations working only from home work times have invaded private life times. The risk is to never disconnect [19, 23]. Instead, it is important to safeguard recovering time both for the well-being of the worker and for his productivity, as had already been underlined by the pre-pandemic research on the risks of technology [12,15,16].

For the future of remote working, it is necessary to work on the times and rights of disconnection and on new organizational methods, as well as on the training of workers in knowing how to manage their time if regulated in a more flexible way [24].

Finally, pandemic research reports a decrease in well-being in working only in remote working with respect to social relationships. The loss of the dimension of informality makes work heavier, less pleasant and sometimes makes the flow of information difficult [25]. In some cases it amplifies the hierarchy.

Research carried out in the pandemic does not return unambiguous or unidirectional results but allow us to identify two important keys in organizational change and activity planning for designing an advantageous use for companies and workers [23, 24].

6.2 Physical environment, comfort and health

If there has been a wide range of comfort surveys on schools, office buildings and other working environments, the comfort conditions at homes and in the residential sector, has been less investigated. Instead, with the wide adoption of home working conditions, there has been the need to investigate how "relaxed controlled" environments such as home desks and similar can have on the worker wellbeing, satisfaction and productivity.

To investigate comfort in buildings, next to physical and time-related factors, it has been demonstrated that it is necessary to take into account "individual" factors of occupants [1], such as the personal background, energy-related attitudes, age, gender or health conditions, educational level, social grade, household size, family income, energy use awareness [27]. At the same time, creating comfortable and healthy indoor environments makes it necessary to face, at the same time, the

challenges related to rising energy costs, reducing energy consumption, mitigating extreme weather conditions and power outages.

Most of the studies on home working were done during the wide spread of the teleworking during the COVID-19 restrictions and have showed that there is a drop in both comfort and ergonomics of home workplaces **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** Moreover, they suggest that there is the need to maintain a certain physical activity level, together with the indoor environment conditions and ergonomics to avoid physical related negative effects (weight gain, poor sleep quality, musculoskeletal pain) and mental related ones (anxiety, depression, stress, headache, fatigue, and lower job satisfaction) [29].

From the environmental point of view, it is suggested in [30] that if commuting distances are above 10 km, the Working From Homes (WFH) always reduces the environmental impact of the worker.

The sudden COVID-19 pandemic requirements found both employees and employers unready to set requirements for telework in place. At the same time, this pointed out – among others – the need of ergonomic interventions including ergonomic training and individual ergonomic assessments for those who work from home [31].

As regards the methods, usually surveys on and correlations between self-reported complaints and physical discomfort and home office characteristics are used [32], [33]. In other cases, artificial intelligence methods are used to support the rearrangement of indoor spaces to maximize the indoor environmental quality index in terms of thermal, acoustic and visual comfort [34]. There is the need to investigate both qualitative and quantitative measures of occupant experience and besides traditional sensing instruments, wearable sensors (e.g. wristbands) can be used [35].

The spread of IT instruments and systems has been another research line, discussing the effects of workers prolonged screen exposure on health and wellbeing [36]. As regards the exposure to screen, the lighting environment plays a crucial role and has been investigated by means of questionnaires [37] but there is the need to perform more objective measurements in order to investigate their correlation with subjective surveys. Also the noise has been identified as a source of distraction in WFH during COVID-19 [38].

Some studies suggested that satisfaction with daylight, artificial light, greenery, and views outside were directly related to satisfaction (mental health variables) while satisfaction with temperature, noise, ventilation, and air quality did not seem to play a role at the home workplace [39]. This has to be further investigated, out of the context of WFH during the COVID-19 pandemic. The relation between health, satisfaction and lighting has gaining increasing interest. Some studies have already proposed home lighting recommendations to that regard [40].

6.3 Nature and biophilia

Biophilia is the innate human tendency to be fascinated by Nature and, in some circumstances, to become emotionally affiliated with it. Biophilic design has been suggested to meet this need. Over the past 15 years, several biophilic design models have been suggested, which have often been implemented in advanced building certification systems. However, biophilic design remains largely empirical and there have been very few projects subjected to an experimental verification plan. Integrating biophilic elements into co-working spaces, such as green walls, natural light, and indoor plants, not only enhances the aesthetic appeal but also improves air quality, reduces stress levels, and enhances collaboration among individuals. By incorporating biophilic design principles in co-working spaces, we embrace the idea that a closer connection with Nature enhances our cognitive abilities, boosts mood, and encourages a sense of community, leading to a more fulfilling and inspiring work experience for all.

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7 Conclusion

This literature review highlights at least three general findings useful for the continuation of the project. The first is that remote working has both benefits and criticalities very clear and recurring even in different lines of research. Of course, the benefits will be enhanced in the next steps of the project while the critical points will have to be smoothed out, where possible, or at least always kept in mind in the industrial research work. Furthermore, the perception of workers and managers about remote working is often a key element in this trade-off between costs and benefits. Second, although there are studies prior to COVID-19, it is only in recent years that the topic has begun to be investigated systematically. It follows that the studies are very recent, and the scientific debate is still a bit rough. Furthermore, the results could be specific to the emergency context in which it mainly took place. Finally, it should be emphasized that the specific features of mountain locations (the central theme of our Spoke 4) have not yet been explored in a detailed and rigorous manner. At the most, some scholars highlight how remote working is heterogeneous between sectors. Only one paper analysed the relevance of territorial elements to correctly understand the effects of remote working.

These last two remarks make the results of the literature review only partially extendable for our purposes. For example, many mountain areas are still characterized by connectivity problems, which can limit the range of activities that can be carried out remotely. Furthermore, the natural beauty of mountain areas can be an additional factor of attraction for high-skilled workers, which can decide to work remotely for some days a week or for some periods of the year. Therefore, further analyses are needed to achieve the project objectives. In particular, extensive field analysis will be required to tailor and support the literature review's results in our specific context.